

Position Uncertainty in a Statistical View of Quantum Bound States

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Derivations of statistical mechanical distributions often involve the maximization of some type of uncertainty (i.e. the number of spatial arrangements or arrangements in degenerate cells of phase space) subject to a global constraint on energy (and also particle number). Interactions within statistical systems (particles colliding with each other or with a wall), introducing conservation of energy at a particle collision level is a way to achieve global energy conservation. Quantum mechanics is a statistical theory, so one may ask whether it too is based on the conservation of a particle property and whether it makes use of the maximization of some type of uncertainty. In this note, we argue that momentum is the conserved particle quantity (kinetic and potential energy are conserved on average) and that for a momentum state, one maximizes the uncertainty of x in a particular way.

Statistical Mechanics

Statistical mechanics seems to be strongly linked to the maximization of uncertainty subject to a constraint on the number of particles: $\sum_i n_i = N$ and the total energy: $\sum_i e_i n_i = E_{\text{total}}$. For example, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained from the maximization of $\ln [N! / \prod_i n_i!]$ subject to the constraints. The Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions may be obtained by maximizing uncertainty in phase space degenerate cells subject to the constraint i.e.

$$\text{FD maximize } \ln [g(e_i)! / [n(e_i)! (g(e_i)-n(e_i))!] \quad ((1a))$$

$$\text{BE maximize } \ln [(g(e)-1+n(e_i))! / ((g(e_i)-1)! n(e_i)!) \quad ((1b)) \text{ both subject to the above constraints.}$$

The MB may also be obtained from the expressions for the FD and BE by setting $g(e_i) \gg n(e_i)$.

These distributions may also be obtained by considering reaction balance for elastic collisions. If energy is conserved at a collision level, this guarantees the global energy constraint. The arrangement approach discussed above is based on the idea of maximizing uncertainty. Is there maximization of uncertainty in the reaction approach? We argue that all reactions with the same energy $e_i + e_j = e$ have the same probability, unless there are extra collision related constraints. Thus, after a collision between particles with energy e , one has complete uncertainty as to the final particle energies, except that they add to e . (One assumes that one does not know the momenta of the incoming particles in this statistical approach.)

For example:

$$\text{MB case: } f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((2a))$$

$$\text{FD case: } f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)] f(e_2)[1-f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1-f(e_1)] f(e_4)[1-f(e_2)] \quad ((2b))$$

$$\text{BE case: } f(e_1)[1+f(e_3)] f(e_2)[1+f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1+f(e_1)] f(e_4)[1+f(e_2)] \quad ((2c))$$

Taking the ln of the above and linking to $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ yields the respective distributions.

Thus, scattering (or interactions with photons or phonons in other cases) seems to be key to statistical mechanics, as is a “conservation condition” and the idea of uncertainty.

Quantum Mechanical Bound States

It is often noted that quantum mechanics is a statistical theory because there is a probability $P(x)$ for single bound particle to be at point x (without knowledge of momentum p) and a probability $P(p)$ for it to have a momentum p (without knowledge of x). In classical physics, p and x are known at each point. Furthermore, there is conservation of energy= kinetic energy + $V(x)$ at each point x where p is automatically given by the energy equation.

One may ask: How does quantum mechanics change this picture? Consider a point x . If one knows p at this point, one has classical physics. If one does not know p , one has a statistical theory i.e. there should be probabilities for different p at each x . This immediately leads to the idea of an average kinetic energy at point x i.e.

$$\text{KE average}(x) = \frac{[\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \quad a(p)f(p,x)]}{[\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) f(p,x)]} \quad ((3))$$

Thus, there is an x dependent normalization constant $W(x)=[\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) f(p,x)]$
Furthermore, KE average(x) should satisfy a classical conservation of energy equation:

$$\text{KE average}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

$f(p,x)$ at this point is completely unknown. A statistical theory has been introduced, but no collision conservation value has been assigned (only an average conservation equation has been suggested) and no maximum uncertainty appears (although momentum is uncertain at each x).

If p is uncertain at each point x , one may ask what is causing this behaviour? It seems it must be $V(x)$ acting in a stochastic manner. Thus, at each point x , $V(x)$ is an average, but in reality may be imparting various momentum hits with different probabilities. Imagine that $f(p,x)$ form a complete set (orthonormal basis). Then, one may write:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k f(p,x) \quad ((5))$$

Here, it is assumed that no matter what the x value, $f(p,x)$ transfers a momentum of p to a colliding particle.

Next, consider the normalization constant $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) f(p,x)$. This represents the momentum distribution of the particle at each point x . This distribution interacts with the $V(x)$ distribution, but does not change because one has an equilibrium or resonance situation.

Consider equation ((4)) and multiply by $W(x)$ i.e.

$$\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) f(p,x) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((6))$$

Let us make the assumption that: $f(p_1,x) f(p_2,x) = f(p_1+p_2,x)$ ((7)) i.e. there is conservation of momentum in collisions with the potential. In such a case, given that $f(p,x)$ is a basis:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) f(p,x) + \left[\sum_k V(k) a(p-k) \right] f(p,x) = E f(p,x) \quad ((8))$$

$f(p,x)$, however, is unknown except for its suggested property ((7)).

One may write: $V(x)W(x) = \sum_k b_k f(k,x)$, but it would be good to have V_k be associated with a transfer of k of momentum in a momentum conserved hit with a particle. This is the reasoning for ((7)).

In classical physics, if one moves from x_1 to x_2 , the kinetic energy changes in accordance with $KE + V(x) = E$. The same holds for average kinetic energy in bound state quantum mechanics, but not for $f(p,x)$. $f(p,x)$ represents the same kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ at each x , but with a different probability. Thus, there is a kind of uncertainty in x as $f(p,x)$ is an object which travels through x with the same momentum p . ((8)) is independent of x even though average kinetic energy is not.

If $f(p_1,x)f(p_2,x) = f(p_1+p_2,x)$ due to momentum conservation and $f(p,x_1)$ and $f(p,x_2)$ have the same kinetic energy, then it seems that:

$$f(p,x_1+x_2) = f(p,x_1)f(p,x_2) \quad ((9))$$

for x uncertainty. If one looks at ((8)), $f(p,x)$ cancels, but it suggests also that $f(p,x_1+x_2) = f(p,x_1)f(p,x_2)$ because the equation should not be distinguished by x . In other words, without cancelling $f(p,x)$ in ((8)), given an $f(p,x_1+x_2)$, the x_2 portion should cancel out to leave ((8)) as an equation in $f(p,x_1)$, where x_1 and x_2 can take any value. Imposing ((9)) seems to give maximum statistical uncertainty to x . This may be seen further in the solution. Thus, one has two sets of uncertainties at the same time, one in p and one in x , but the one in p is restricted by the conservation of average energy.

A possible solution is a^{-bp^2} where b is a constant. If x is large, $f(p,x)$ goes to 0, but this does not seem to be good, because one may have a quantum particle in a very large box. There is no reason for $f(p,x)$ to grow or drop as x becomes very large. This leads to the suggestion that b be complex. Then one may rewrite $f(p,x) = \exp(-ipx)$.

The fact that $f(p,x)$ is complex is interesting in that its modulus is 1, indicating complete uncertainty in x . This seems to be in keeping with the idea of maximum uncertainty in statistical systems. It should be noted that in most of our previous notes regarding quantum mechanics, we start with the form $\exp(ipx)$ and then make generalizations. In this note, we try to argue that $\exp(ipx)$ emerges through statistical considerations and the idea of introducing uncertainty.

In quantum mechanics, $\exp(ipx)$ is usually taken as a solution of a differential equation and then it is pointed out that its modulus is 1 and there is complete uncertainty in x . We try to use the reverse thinking by imposing complete uncertainty in x due to statistical reasons and obtaining $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution which follows without using a differential equation.

The symmetry of x and p in $\exp(ipx)$ suggests that this function may also be related to the case of having a fixed p and considering all x positions, although one does not have the average conservation of energy equation in this case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may attempt to create a statistical theory which treats $V(x)$, the potential, and kinetic energy at x as average values. Thus, conservation of energy $KE(x)+V(x)=E$ holds only for averages. As a result, a particle at x should have a probability $f(p,x)/W(x)$ to have momentum p . This distribution comes from $V(x)$ which should also have a momentum distribution $V(x)=\sum_k V_k f(k,x)$. We argue that the kinetic energy represented by $f(p,x)/W(x)$ is independent of position, although its weight is not. We also try to argue that $f(p_1,x)f(p_2,x)=f(p_1+p_2,x)$ on the basis of conservation of momentum when a particle collides with a p wave of the potential. This leads to a possible solution of $f(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$. The fact that it is complex is not alarming as its modulus is 1. $f(p,x)$ represents an entity which has the same kinetic energy at all x , so there is no reason why it should either increase or decrease with x , although $f(p,x)/W(x)$ may decrease or increase. Thus, we try to argue that quantum mechanics for bound states may be thought of as a statistical theory which involves microscopic scattering which conserve a quantity, namely momentum, and ensure maximum uncertainty (in x) for $f(p,x)$.